

Educational resources for non-technical stakeholders in training

1. Introduction

The educational resources of the In Silico World project aim to train or retrain different key groups in the development and use of in silico models in the medical field. One of these key groups is the group of master and PhD students that are being trained in a non-technical discipline related to the medical field. Although they can have various backgrounds, i.e. in medical sciences, pharmaceutical sciences, nursery, etc., they have in common that they are related to the medical field, while having only a limited training in mathematics or engineering. Concrete lecture material was developed in the format of a mini-course that contains three important topics in the field of in silico medicine. A shortened version of the lecture material was tested by a participant group. Its impact was then evaluated based on a pre- and post-questionnaire, on the one hand, and an in-depth analysis of the pre-defined learning goals, on the other hand. Based on the results, recommendations on the further use and optimization of the lecture material are formulated.

2. Methods

While many topics related to in silico medicine are of interest and not much educational resources are already available for non-technical stakeholders, a selection of topics was first of all made by determining intended learning outcomes for the considered participant group at the initial stage. In order to develop educational resources, a mini-course was composed. This mini-course contains three modules, each on a different topic, and aims to make the participants familiar with some basic aspects of in silico modeling in medicine and get a view on the state-of-the-art research. An overview of the considered topics in the mini-course and the total duration of each module can be found in table 1. A short description of the content can be found in appendix A.

Table 1: Overview of the topics and the duration for the modules of the developed mini-course.

Module	Topic	Duration full version (min.)	Duration short version (min.)
1	Introduction to in silico medicine	90	40
2	Validation of experiments	85	25
3	Example cases	40	15

In order to collect data and feedback on the composed lecture material, a test version of the mini-course was set up based on a selection of fragments from the video recordings. This selection allows the participants to grasp the main concepts of the lecture in a limited time frame. Next to the selection of fragments, the test version included a pre- and post-questionnaire, as well as an evaluation form after each topic of the mini-course. The total time of the test version was estimated at two hours. This short version was tested by eight participants, with a non-technical background in pharmaceutical or medical sciences.

The pre- and post-questionnaire assessed how aware the participants were on different concepts related to in silico medicine and to which extent they agreed to statements that expressed the potential added value of this domain before and after going through the lecture material, by selecting one of five predefined categories. The categories were not aware, slightly aware, moderately aware,

very aware and extremely aware for the questions and strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree and strongly agree for the statements. Those categories were translated into a numerical score, ranging from one to five. A histogram of the given scores was made for the answers of the pre- and post-questionnaire as well as the difference in pre- and post-score per participant.

Next to the data analysis based on the questionnaires, an in-depth analysis was performed as well. In the evaluation forms, the participants were asked to indicate the three key aspects they wanted to take home. By relating these aspects to the learning goals of each module, an indication was found of the extent to which the learning goals were effectively achieved. While three key aspects were asked for in the questionnaire, the number of indicated learning goals per participant and per module could vary, depending on how well the provided key aspects could be related to one or more learning goals. In most cases, however, three learning goals were maximally indicated. Each learning goal was only indicated once per participants. Moreover, the stakeholders had the possibility to include written feedback in the form as well.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Analysis of questionnaires

The initial scores given to the questions of the pre-questionnaires are on average in the lower half of the awareness-categories, which confirms the need for lecture material on in silico modeling in medicine for non-technical stakeholders in training. This is not only the case for the average value, but also most of the individual scores are initially situated in the lower half of the range, as can be observed from the histograms of the scores per question (see appendix B). Nevertheless, the extent to which they agree with the statements, and therefore the believe in the potential added value of in silico medicine, is on average much higher. The fact that the considered participants voluntarily decided to participate might of course impose an intrinsic bias to the initial interest in the topic.

When comparing the average results of the pre- and post-questionnaire, a slight increase is observed (see figure 1). This indicates that, in general, the participants have the idea that they have more knowledge on specific topics and agree better with statements on the potential added value of in silico modeling in medicine. The average increase in perceived knowledge related to artificial intelligence, Bayesian network models, pharmacokinetic models and verification was very low. These aspects are indeed not covered profoundly in the mini-course, which likely explains the limited increase. In particular, the increase in awareness on validation is considered to be valuable. This is one of the aspects participants with a non-technical background should be well aware of, in order to critically apply and/or interpret results from in silico medicine.

Figure 1: (a) Mean scores of the questions in the pre- and post-questionnaire regarding the perceived awareness of various in silico medicine concepts. (b) Mean scores of the extent of agreement to the statements in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

The participant-specific differences between the pre- and post-questionnaire indicates either a status quo or slight increase in the given score. Only in a few cases, the awareness was perceived to be lower after going through the lecture material. The participant-specific results illustrate that not only on average, but also on an individual level, a slight, but quite consistent increase was observed (see appendix B).

While a major increase in the perceived knowledge remains absent, an overall slight increase in the, initially low, participant awareness was observed. The test version of the mini-course, therefore, shows that the lecture material can help to familiarize non-technical stakeholders with in silico modeling in medicine, already during their education. Of course, following the complete mini-course is expected to further enhance this effect, as grasping the full story might help to build up the knowledge in a more coherent manner. While this mini-course does not attempt to transform participants into experts in in silico medicine, it might help to initiate their high-level knowledge. Longer and more specific courses are needed in a next step to further enhance their knowledge of the use, applications and potential added value of in silico modeling in medicine.

While the interest in following these courses was not directly assessed, the extent of agreement gives an indication of the participants' believe in the potential added value of integrating in silico modeling in medicine. Although the initial believe showed already a high score, the lecture material succeeded to further increase this believe and, therefore, tends to enhance the interest in the topic. This is a crucial aspect in convincing stakeholders to initiate further education on this topic.

3.2. In-depth analysis of learning goals

The extent to which the learning goals could be identified in the key aspects provided by the participants, is illustrated in figure 2. The height of the bars indicate the fraction of participants that provided key aspects that could be related to a specific learning goal (see appendix A). The color of the bars shows an *a priori* identification of the extent to which the learning goals were covered in the test version of the lecture material. Green, orange and red, respectively, refer to a learning goal that is well, moderately or not covered in the test version. None of the learning goals were considered to be completely absent in the test version in this case, which explains the absence of red bars.

Figure 2: Frequency of indication of learning of (a) module 1, (b) module 2 and (c) module 3. The height of the colored bar indicates the fraction of participants that provided key aspects related to the considered learning goals. The color of the bar as well as the background indicates how well the learning goal was covered in the test version of the lecture material, with green and orange respectively referring to well and moderately covered.

While the relation between the provided key aspects and the learning goals is subject to interpretation and the frequency of indication depends on the number of learning goals for each modules, the figure gives an estimation of the combined effect of the aspects that are of interest to the participants and the information that the participant retains from the lecture material.

Overall, most of the learning goals were indicated in the key aspects of, at least, part of the participants. The frequency of indication and its relation to the amount of attention that was spend to the goal in the test version of the mini-course was, however, variable. Some of the learning goals that were expected to be well covered in the short version of the lecture material, were indeed frequently indicated in the key aspects of the participants. This confirms that, at least, part of the content of the lecture material was grasped by the participants. Surprisingly, some of the learning goals that were only moderately covered in the test version were still frequently identified, while some of the well covered learning goals were not indicated well. On the one hand, this might also indicate that a learning goal should be addressed more explicitly in order to ensure that the participants grasp the envisioned content, in particular for those goals that have a lower frequency of indication than expected. On the other hand, this effect could be related to the interest of the participants and, therefore, provide information on the topics the participants are interested in, which can contribute to the further optimization of the lecture material.

First of all, learning goals that were considered to be well covered in the test version and that were often indicated as key aspects should retain their importance in an optimized version of the mini-course. Learning goals that were frequently indicated, while the goal was only moderately covered, do not imply an immediate change of the lecture material. In the complete mini-course, more attention is already provided to the considered goal, which is expected to be sufficient. Nevertheless, these topics are expected to be of interest to the participants. In more specialized or elaborate courses, it could, therefore, be relevant to provide more in-depth information on the topic.

Learning goals that were only indicated to a limited extent, compared to the *a priori* expectations, deserve additional attention in the optimization of the lecture material. Indeed, the first stage is to reconsider the importance of the learning goal. If the learning goal is still considered to be important, than the way the content is provided should be reconsidered. Making the mini-course more interactive or adding more motivating examples could contribute to help the participant in grasping the content.

Moreover, it should be noted that the current evaluation format, i.e. asking for three key aspects, is prone to interpretation. Therefore, an assessment with multiple choice questions could provide valuable objective information on the grasped knowledge of the participants.

4. Outlook

Based on a quantitative analysis, the effect of the lecture material on the awareness of in silico medicine and believe in its potential added value is promising. While the size of the test group was limited, these results indicate that a short amount of lecture material already has a slight positive effect on the knowledge on in silico modelling in medicine. In this respect, more elaborate lecture material is expected to further enhance this effect.

The in-depth analysis indicates to which extent the learning goals were considered to be key aspects by the participants. This gives combined information of the interest of the participants and how well they grasped the learning goals. It is strongly recommended to include this information in further optimization of the lecture material, in particular for those learning goals that resulted in a lower frequency of identification compared to the initial expectations.

The written feedback identified mainly that the lecture on validation of experiments was often too technical. It is, therefore, suggested to edit the video material and add short descriptions to clarify the meaning of technical terms.

Moreover a short self-assessment after following the mini-course could help the stakeholder to assess their knowledge on the discussed topics in a more objective way, compared to the questionnaire where only their perception of awareness was queried. As a proof of concept, some assessment-questions were already implemented to showcase the suggested improvement of the lecture material.

Appendix A – Modules of mini-course with learning goals

Module 1: Introduction to in silico medicine

This course module introduces the participants to some of the general concepts of in silico medicine technologies and discusses the related opportunities and limitations.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Understand the complexity of dealing with predictions about human health;
2. Identify the origins of barriers against adoption of in silico technologies (complexity, redundancy, stochasticity, culture);
3. Summarize first examples of Digital Twins and In Silico Trials developed;
4. Assess the value of the In Silico Trials in the development of new medical products;
5. Outline the 3R concept that led In Silico Trials;
6. Illustrate how In silico technologies might be of help to ensure and extend the healthcare given how the world population is growing;
7. Explain what the Virtual Human Twin will be.

Module 2: Experimental validation of models

An in silico model can only be considered credible when it is properly validated with an experiment. The course module indicates how such a validation experiment can be developed and illustrates this with state-of-the-art examples.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Explain the difference between numeric, epistemic and aleatoric errors in in silico modeling;
2. Identify the five requirements to develop a credible validation framework and apply those to a state-of-the-art research problem;
3. Formulate the difference in characteristics of numerical models and in vitro experiments;
4. Summarize two examples of in silico models and how they can be experimentally validated;
5. Clarify the meaning of the modeling concepts registration, segmentation and meshing, together with their role in the validation process.

Module 3: Example cases

This course module provides the participants with state-of-the-art examples of in silico medicine models that are in different stages of their development and have the perspective of being used in the clinical practice and/or the development of improved treatment strategies.

An overview of the learning goals is given below.

1. Illustrate the added value of in silico medicine with state-of-the-art examples;
2. Link the general concepts related to in silico modeling to state-of-the-art examples;
3. Summarize the state-of-the-art of in silico medicine in two different domains.

Appendix B – Participant-specific results

Question 1: Computational mechanics

Figure B1: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 1 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 1 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 2: Multiscale modeling

Figure B2: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 2 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 2 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 3: Artificial intelligence

Figure B3: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 3 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 3 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 4: Pharmacokinetic models

Figure B4: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 4 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 4 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 5: (Bayesian) network models

Figure B5: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 5 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 5 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 6: Agent based models

Figure B6: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 6 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 6 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 7: Molecular modeling

Figure B7: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 7 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 7 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 8: Uncertainty quantification

Figure B8: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 8 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 8 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 9: Verification

Figure B9: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 9 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 9 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Question 10: Validation

Figure B10: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on awareness question 10 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to awareness question 10 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Statement 1: Accelerate adoption of new medical device or treatment

Figure B11: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on statement 1 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to statement 1 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Statement 2: Decrease number of clinical trials conducted on humans or animals

Figure B12: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on statement 2 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to statement 2 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.

Statement 3: Decrease cost to develop medical device or treatment

Figure B13: (a) Histogram of the difference between the score on statement 3 of the pre- and post-questionnaire per participant. (b) Histogram of the scores given by each participant to statement 3 in the pre- and post-questionnaire.